

A Study of Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycines with Some Metals Ions. Part XV. N-*p* Toluene-sulphonyl (dl) α - and β -Alanines

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N-*p*-Toluenesulphonyl (dl) α - and β -alanines ($R_t^{\alpha}H_2$ and $R_t^{\beta}H_2$) form complex compounds with Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I). Electronic and i.r. spectral data of most Cu(II) complexes and of the ligands $R_t^{\alpha}H_2$ and $R_t^{\beta}H_2$ are recorded. Magnetic moments of all Cu(II) complexes have also been determined and a discussion has been made.

In our earlier communications, complex compounds formed by the chelating agents—N-benzenesulphonyl (dl) α - and β -alanines ($R_b^{\alpha}H_2$ and $R_b^{\beta}H_2$)¹, and N-*p*-toluenesulphonyl glycine (R_tH_2)² were described and gave interesting results that led us to study the reaction of N-*p*-toluenesulphonyl (dl) α - and β -alanines ($R_t^{\alpha}H_2$ and $R_t^{\beta}H_2$) with different metal cations.

Complex compounds of Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) isolated employing $R_t^{\alpha}H_2$, are closely comparable to those of R_bH_2 -N-benzenesulphonyl glycine³, $R_b^{\alpha}H_2$ and R_tH_2 , and with the chelating agent $R_t^{\beta}H_2$ to those of $R_b^{\beta}H_2$. The compound $\text{Cu}(R_t^{\alpha}H_2)_2$ is a weak dibasic acid, but $\text{Cu}(R_t^{\beta}H_2)_2$ decomposes on treating with alkali and the same has also been observed in the case of $\text{Cu}(R_b^{\beta}H_2)_2$.

Experimental

All chemicals employed were either A.R. grade or properly purified. Electronic absorption spectra were measured with Hilger's UVISPEK spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra were obtained following KBr disc technique and magnetic susceptibilities were measured with a Gouy balance. Conductance measurements were made with a Phillip's RCL Bridge PP 9030 and pH measurements with a Cambridge portable-type pH-meter.

Preparation and properties of the ligands and their metal chelates :

N-*p*-toluenesulphonyl (dl) α - and β -alanines ($R_t^{\alpha}H_2$ and $R_t^{\beta}H_2$) were prepared following the methods

stated in the literature^{4,5}, having melting points 139° and 122° respectively.

Methods of isolation of complex compounds of Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) with $R_t^{\alpha}H_2$ were similar to the preparation of such complexes with R_bH_2 , $R_b^{\alpha}H_2$ and $R_b^{\beta}H_2$, and with $R_t^{\beta}H_2$ to those with $R_b^{\beta}H_2$. Complex compounds isolated and their analyses are stated in Table 1.

By potentiometric titration of $\text{Cu}(R_t^{\alpha}H_2)_2$ at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) using requisite amount of NaClO_4 at $32^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$, pK^*_2 and pK^*_1 were evaluated by projection-strip method⁶ and are stated in Table 2. The corresponding values of $\text{Cu}(R_bH_2)_2$, $\text{Cu}(R_tH_2)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(R_b^{\alpha}H_2)_2$ are also included in Table 2 for comparison.

The magnetic moments after diamagnetic corrections⁷ of all Cu(II) complexes and electronic spectra of water-soluble Cu(II) chelates and ligands along with their sodium salts, were determined at room temperature and the data are stated in Table 3.

The magnetic susceptibilities (χ) at low temperatures in the cases of $[\text{Cu}(R_t^{\alpha}H)(\text{OH})]_2$, $\text{Cu}(R_t^{\alpha}H)_2 \cdot 3.5H_2O$ and $\text{Cu}(R_t^{\beta}H)_2$ were also measured. The compound $[\text{Cu}(R_t^{\alpha}H)(\text{OH})]_2$ obeyed Curie-Weiss law over the temperature range 303°K to 78°K with Weiss constant $\theta = +5^{\circ}\text{K}$. The magnetic moment of 1.97 ± 0.07 B.M. which was found to be independent of temperature in the range 303°K to 78°K corresponded to normal magnetic moment values of Cu(II) complexes. But the compound has been stated as $[\text{Cu}(R_t^{\alpha}H)(\text{OH})]_2$ containing two atoms of Cu(II) and anti-ferromagnetic interaction could not be detected in the temperature range 303°K to 78°K. This might be due to much greater Cu-Cu distance than that for such interaction, (c.f. ref. 15, p. 110, the magnetic moment of pale-blue Cu(II) salicylate tetrahydrate is 1.92 B.M. in conformity with the large Cu-Cu distance 3.728Å). On the other hand, the compounds $\text{Cu}(R_t^{\alpha}H)_2$, $3.5H_2O$ and $\text{Cu}(R_t^{\beta}H)_2$

TABLE I. ANALYTICAL DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES.

Compound	% Metal		% Nitrogen		% Sodium		% Loss at 110°	
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
Cu(R _t ^a H)(OH)(H ₂ O)	18.61	18.66	4.06	4.11	—	—	5.27	5.29
[Cu(R _t ^a H)(OH)] ₂	19.54	19.70	4.32	4.34	—	—	—	—
Cu(R _t ^a H) ₂ ·3.5H ₂ O	10.35	10.41	4.52	4.59	—	—	10.26	10.31
Cu(R _t ^a H) ₂	11.55	11.61	5.05	5.11	—	—	—	—
Na ₂ Cu(R _t ^a) ₂	10.71	10.74	4.69	4.74	7.79	7.78	—	—
Zn(R _t ^a H) ₂	11.84	11.90	4.92	5.10	—	—	—	—
Cd(R _t ^a H)(OH)(H ₂ O)	28.80	28.86	3.54	3.59	—	—	—	—
Cd(R _t ^a H) ₂	18.79	18.85	4.66	4.70	—	—	—	—
Hg(R _t ^a H)(OH)(H ₂ O)	41.14	42.01	2.90	2.93	—	—	—	—
Na ₂ Hg(R _t ^a) ₂	27.40	27.53	3.78	3.84	6.35	6.31	—	—
Ag(R _t ^a H)	30.84	30.84	3.99	4.00	—	—	—	—
Cu(R _t ^β H) ₂	11.52	11.61	5.08	5.11	—	—	—	—
Zn(R _t ^β H) ₂	11.91	11.90	5.04	5.10	—	—	—	—
Cd(R _t ^β H) ₂	18.73	18.85	4.64	4.70	—	—	—	—
Hg(R _t ^β H)(OH)(H ₂ O)	41.90	42.01	2.87	2.93	—	—	—	—
Na ₂ Hg(R _t ^β) ₂	27.40	27.53	3.82	3.84	6.29	6.31	—	—
Ag(R _t ^β H)	30.83	30.84	3.96	4.00	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2. ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF COMPLEX ACIDS—
Cu(RH)₂

Complex acids	Cu(R _b H) ₂	Cu(R _t H) ₂	Cu(R _b ^a H) ₂	Cu(R _t ^a H) ₂
pK ₂ *	4.51	4.55	4.70	4.75
pK ₁ *	7.23	7.24	7.10	7.10

were found to exhibit anti-ferromagnetism. The exact position⁸ of the maxima were established from

graphical plots of $\frac{\Delta\chi}{\Delta T}$ against the temperature T ,

the intercept of the T -axis at $\frac{\Delta\chi}{\Delta T} = 0$ being taken

as the Curie or Néel temperature T_c , and J in °K values were calculated from the relation $T_c = 5\theta/2 = 5J/8^9$. Results are stated in Table 4.

In the case of Cu(R_t^aH)₂·3.5H₂O, above the temperature T_c , χ_A (the molar magnetic susceptibility after diamagnetic corrections) fell gradually, but Curie-Weiss law had not been established at 303°K. Below T_c susceptibility χ_A fell rapidly so that at 109°K, it was only near about one-third of the maximum value. Data regarding the compound Cu(R_t^βH)₂, were also found to be closely comparable

to that of Cu(R_t^aH)₂·3.5H₂O. Curie-Weiss law had not been established at 303°K and below T_c the χ_A values also fell but less rapidly so that at 109°K, it was about two-third of the maximum value. At temperatures well above J , it could be shown that Curie-Weiss law would hold.

The compound [Cu(R_t^aH)(OH)]₂ is insoluble in all common solvents and the compounds Cu(R_t^aH)₂·3.5H₂O and Cu(R_t^βH)₂ are moderately soluble in hot water and practically insoluble in cold water. But their molecular weights could not be determined by ebullioscopy in aqueous solution due to decomposition on boiling.

The i.r. spectra of most Cu(II) complexes, R_t^aH₂ and R_t^βH₂ in KBr matrix were also measured and the assignments¹⁰⁻¹² of some important vibrations are recorded in Table 5.

Discussion

The normal magnetic moment values (1.8–2.2 B.M.)¹³ are observed in the present cases for Cu(II) complexes excepting of Cu(R_t^aH)₂ and Cu(R_t^βH)₂, where subnormal values^{14,15} have been found. By temperature variation magnetic susceptibility measurements they are found to exhibit antiferromagnetism as has been found in the case of Cu(II) acetate monohydrate. Therefore these low values may be due to metal-metal interaction in an octahedral structure which is closely comparable to

TABLE 3. MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF Cu(II) COMPLEXES AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF WATER-SOLUBLE Cu(II) COMPLEXES AND THE LIGANDS

Species	λ_{max} in nm	log ϵ	Temperature °K	μ_{eff} in B.M.
Cu(R ^{<i>a</i>} H)(OH)(H ₂ O)	—	—	303	2.02
[Cu(R ^{<i>a</i>} H)(OH)] ₂	—	—	303	1.95
Cu(R ^{<i>a</i>} H) ₂ ·3.5H ₂ O	760, 320, 272, 263, 258, 232	1.32, 1.88, 2.98, 3.25, 3.20, 4.10	303	1.39
Na ₂ Cu(R ^{<i>a</i>} H) ₂	660, 310(sh), 273, 265, 223	1.68, 2.81, 3.13, 3.42, 4.08	303	1.82
Cu(R ^{<i>b</i>} H) ₂	760, 325, 265, 223	1.28, 1.83, 3.30, 4.01	303	1.49
R ^{<i>a</i>} H ₂	272, 264, 234	2.64, 2.78, 3.62	—	—
Na(R ^{<i>a</i>} H)	271, 264, 232	2.60, 2.75, 3.59	—	—
R ^{<i>b</i>} H ₂	272, 265, 231	2.62, 2.78, 3.60	—	—
Na(R ^{<i>b</i>} H)	271, 265, 232	2.58, 2.80, 3.56	—	—

TABLE 4. TEMPERATURE VARIATION MAGNETIC DATA OF Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂·3.5H₂O AND Cu(R^{*b*}H)₂

Species	T _c in °K	J in °K	χ_A in C.G.S. units × 10 ⁶
Cu(R ^{<i>a</i>} H) ₂ ·3.5H ₂ O	292	467	780
Cu(R ^{<i>b</i>} H) ₂	274	438	963

Cu(II) salts of organic fatty acids. However, the dimeric nature of such compounds is also supported by i.r. spectral data^{16,17}. Thus their structures are similar to Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂ and the structure of [Cu(R^{*a*}H)(OH)]₂ may also be assigned as that of [Cu(R^{*a*}H)(OH)]₂ having a binuclear one with diol bridge arrangement, which has been described in an earlier communication².

The i.r. spectral data show that marked shifts of the band at 1725–1727 cm⁻¹ (ligands) to lower frequencies in the complexes and shifts in –SO₂N < stretching frequencies from 1346–1341 cm⁻¹ (ligands) to lower frequencies—supporting the presence of M–O and M–N bonding respectively in the complexes. The shift in –SO₂N < stretch is much more appreciable in the case of Na₂Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂, which may be associated with the dissociation of imido-hydrogen, resulting in a stronger M–N bond. The disappearance of N–H stretch supports dissociation of imido-hydrogen and formation of Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂²⁻ anion. The bands for M–N and M–O stretches are also observed in the complexes.

Electronic absorption spectra of the ligands and their sodium salts in aqueous solution show a number of peaks in the U–V region, possibly due to π – π^* transitions¹¹. In the electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes, the characteristic absorption band¹⁸ in the region 900–600 nm has been observed. In aqueous solution the absorption maxima at 760 nm for Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂ and Cu(R^{*b*}H)₂ and at 660 nm for Na₂Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂ are found and their ϵ_{max} values support

distorted octahedral structures¹⁹ evidently due to water interaction. The blue shift of d–d band of the aqueous solution of the complex acid Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂ on neutralisation indicates that water is more strongly coordinating axial ligand than in Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂²⁻ anion and it is clear that the position of this band is a useful indication of the degree of tetragonal distortion²⁰ supporting square planar or much greater tetragonally distorted structure of Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂²⁻ anion. As indicated by high ϵ_{max} values, absorption peaks in the U–V region are undoubtedly due to ligand molecules

Conductance data of the complex Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂ in aqueous solution are in accordance with the theoretical anticipation²¹ being a weak acid. By potentiometric titration the complex Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂ in aqueous solution, has been shown to be a weak dibasic acid. In earlier communications^{1,2} Cu(R^{*b*}H)₂, Cu(R^{*c*}H)₂ and Cu(R^{*b*}H)₂ have also been described as weak dibasic acids—evidently due to ionisation of imido-hydrogen. Cu(R^{*b*}H)₂ and Cu(R^{*a*}H)₂ decompose at higher pH values, showing less stable. As indicated by the data (pK*₂ values) in Table 2, shifts in the enhancement of acidity of imido-hydrogen on the formation of metal-nitrogen coordination bond, appear to be proportional to the stability of metal chelates²². So the stability of the Cu(II) chelates may be represented in the ligand order R^{*b*}H₂ > R^{*c*}H₂ > R^{*a*}H₂ > R^{*b*}H₂ > R^{*a*}H₂. However it should be mentioned here that such enhancement of acidity of imido-hydrogen on the formation of metal-nitrogen coordination bond, could not be measured in the cases of Cu(R^{*b*}H)₂ and Cu(R^{*b*}H)₂. Both of them decompose on adding alkali and appear to be the most unstable among such complexes studied.

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TABLE 5. I.R. SPECTRAL DATA OF CU(II) COMPLEXES AND LIGANDS

Compounds					Assignments
$R_f^a H_2$	$R_f^b H_2$	$Cu(R_f^a H)_2$	$Na_2Cu(R_f^a)_2$	$Cu(R_f^b H)_2$	
3291(sp st)	3286(sp st)	3241(sp m)	—	3392(sp st)	N-H stretch
1725(sp st)	1727(sp st)	—	—	—	Due to -COOH
—	—	1653(sp st)	1631(sp st)	1605(sp st)	COO ⁻ antisymmetrical stretch.
1453(sp m)	1443(b st)	—	—	—	C-O stretch or O-H deformation.
—	—	1430(sp st)	1389(sp st)	1408(sp m)	COO ⁻ symmetrical stretch.
1346(sp st)	1341(sp st)	1330(sp m)	1256(sp st)	1332(sp st)	Due to -SO ₂ N <
1172(b st)	1168(b st)	1172(sp st)	1139(b st)	1168(sp st)	—
—	—	573(b st)	588(b st)	566(b m)	M-N stretch
—	—	552(b m)	556(sp st)	550(sp st)	M-O stretch.

sp = sharp; b = broad; st = strong; m = medium.

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